

Synthesis of 3-Heteraryl Coumarins as Optical Brighteners

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A few 2-aryl and 2-heterocyclic substituted (6,7) coumarinoxazoles have been synthesised by condensing 6-amino-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin with aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids with the aid of polyphosphoric acid. The ultraviolet, infrared, nmr, mass and fluorescence spectra of these compounds have been presented for characterisation.

7-(2'-Benzoxazolyl)-3-phenylcoumarins¹ and 2-(3'-coumarinyl) benzoxazoles² have been reported to be optical brighteners for polyesters, polyamides and polyvinyl chloride. 2-(3'-Coumarinyl) naphthoxazoles with a dialkylamino substituent in 7-position of the coumarin ring exhibit brilliant fluorescence with absorption in the visible range and are useful for the dyeing of organic fibres³. Coumarin derivatives, specially 3-aryl-7-substituted aminocoumarins, because of their intense blue fluorescence and good light fastness constitute an important group of optical brighteners for synthetic fibres like polyamide and polyester⁴. In our earlier studies⁵ coumarino-oxazoles with aromatic or heterocyclic substitution in 2-position have been found to possess high fluorescence in uv and visible region. Encouraged by these results, in our present investigation, various 2-(3-coumarinyl)-4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5) oxazoles, 2-(3-aryl, 3-naphthyl, 3-heteraryl) oxazoles and bis oxazoles have been synthesized by the condensation of 4-methyl-3-phenyl-6-amino-7-hydroxycoumarin (I) with various substituted coumarin-3-carboxylic acids, aromatic carboxylic acids, naphthoic acids, pyridine carboxylic acids and dicarboxylic acids to get the corresponding oxazoles II, III using polyphosphoric acid as the cyclodehydrating agent.

In addition to the above compounds a few 2-(3'-coumarinyl)-coumarin (3:4) oxazoles have been synthesized to study the effect on fluorescence of oxazole moiety on the pyrone part of the coumarin. For the purpose of synthesizing the

above compounds 3-amino-4-hydroxycoumarin (IV) was condensed with various coumarin-3-carboxylic acids to get the corresponding oxazoles (V) using polyphosphoric acid as cyclodehydrating agent.

The above compounds have been characterized by uv, ir, nmr, mass and fluorescence spectral data.

UV spectra: The uv spectra of all the compounds were recorded on Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer using dioxane as solvent. All the title compounds exhibited three main regions of absorption around 368 ± 30 , 283 ± 5 and 253 ± 10 nm. The fluorescence spectra for all the compounds were measured on Beckmann DK 2A spectrophotometer using dioxane as the solvent. The results are tabulated in Tables 1A, 1B and 1C.

The information obtained from the fluorescence spectrum may be used in the evaluation of the compounds as possible fluorescent brighteners for synthetic fibres, plastics, papers etc. An ideal fluorescent brightener should absorb in the uv region between 340 and 400 nm and emit in the visible region⁶. The maximum of these resulting

TABLE 1A

Sl. No.	2-(Heteraryl)-4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5) oxazole	max. absorption	max. emission	Difference	Colour observed
		nm	nm		
1.	2-(8-Coumarinyl)-	369	455	86	Blue
2.	2-(6-Methyl-8-coumarinyl)-	371	457	86	Blue
3.	2-(8-Methyl-3-coumarinyl)-	369	456	87	Blue
4.	2-(6-Bromo-3-coumarinyl)-	370	469	99	Blue
5.	2-(5,6-Benzo-3-coumarinyl)-	396	488	87	Green
6.	2-(2-Naphthyl)-	359	400	41	Violet
7.	2-(p-Toluyyl)-	342	426	84	Violet
8.	2-(1-Naphthyl)-	369	406	37	Violet
9.	2-(Benzyl)-	329	430	101	Light violet
10.	2-(3-Pyridyl)-	354	408	54	Light violet
11.	2-(4-Pyridyl)-	353.5	410	56.5	Light violet

TABLE 1B

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	max. absorp- tion	max. emis- sion	Diffe- rence	Colour observed
1.	Bis-[4'-methyl-3'-phenyl-coumarino-(6',7': 4,5)-oxazolo] methane	326	437	111	Light violet
2.	Bis-[4'-methyl-3'-phenyl-coumarino (6',7': 4,5) oxazolo] ethylene	408.5	456	47.5	Blue
3.	Bis-1,4-[4'-methyl-3'-phenyl-coumarino (6',7': 4,5)-oxazolo] benzene	393	478	105	Green

TABLE 1C

Sl. No.	2-(3-Heteraryl)-coumarino(8,4': 4,5) oxazole	max. absorp- tion nm	max. emis- sion nm	Diffe- rence	Colour observed
1.	2-(3-Coumarinyl)-	365	455	100	Blue
2.	2-(8-Methyl-3-coumarinyl)-	365	457	92	Blue
3.	2-(6,6-Benzo-3-coumarinyl)-	393	478	115	Green

fluorescent light, which determines the colour ranges, is between 415-465 nm. The fluorescent maxima of all the 2-(3-coumarinyl)-coumarino oxazoles have emission in the ideal range and therefore these compounds are potential optical brighteners.

IR spectra : The ir spectra of the compounds have been recorded on Perkin Elmer Model 137 in KBr. All the coumarino-oxazoles exhibited a strong band around $1730 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of coumarin carbonyl group. In addition, peaks at 1550 to 1570 cm^{-1} , $1100 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1360 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, attributable to >C=N , -C-O-C- and >C=N= of the oxazole system, respectively, have also been found to be common.

NMR spectra : The nmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 nmr spectrophotometer in DMSO and CDCl_3 . The details of the spectra are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—2-(6-METHYL-3-COUMARINYL)-4'-METHYL-3'-PHENYLCOUMARINO-(6',7': 4,5) OXAZOLE

δ values	No. of protons	Assignment
2.45 (s)	3	6 Methyl protons
2.55 (s)	3	4' Methyl protons
7.83-7.55(m)	10	Aromatic protons
8.25(s)	1	Vinyl proton

Mass spectra : The mass spectra was recorded on RMU-6L Mass spectrometer with inlet temperature ranging from 150 to 200° and an electron beam energy of 70 eV . The mass spectrum of 2-(8-methyl-3-coumarinyl)-4'-methyl-3'-phenyl-coumarino-(6',7': 4,5) oxazole has been recorded. The molecular ion peak at m/z 435 is the base peak. The peaks at m/z (% abundance) 407 (95%), 379 (22%), 105 (70%) and 64 (38%) are observed in the mass spectrum of the above compound. The major

fragmentation mode is loss of carbon monoxide as observed in the case of simple coumarins⁷.

Experimental

Preparation of 6-amino-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin : Synthesized from 5-nitroresacetophenone as reported earlier⁸ but with certain modifications in the process of deacetylation and reduction.

5-Nitroresacetophenone (5 g), sodium phenyl acetate (10 g) and acetic anhydride (60 ml) were mixed together and refluxed in an oil bath at 180° for 8 hr. The reaction mixture on pouring in ice water, filtration and recrystallisation from acetic acid yielded 6-nitro-7-acetoxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin, m.p. 201° . 2 g of the above compound was added to 50 ml of 5% sodium carbonate solution and refluxed for 3 hr. On neutralisation, it gave 6-nitro-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin, m.p. 223° .

2.7 g of the above nitro compound was mixed with 7 g sodium dithionite, 30 ml ammonia, 30 ml water and 15 ml rectified spirit, refluxed for 15 min and cooled. The compound separated on recrystallisation gave 6-amino-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin, m.p. 240° .

Preparation of 2-(3-coumarinyl, aryl, heteraryl, naphthyl)-4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5) oxazoles : Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by stirring a mixture of phosphorous pentoxide (15 g) and orthophosphoric acid (10 ml) at 100° for 1 hr. A mixture of 6-amino-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin (0.005 mole) and appropriate acid (0.005 mole) was then dropped into the above. The reaction mixture was heated first at $150-60^\circ$ for 2 hr and then at $200-205^\circ$ for further 2 hr. The reaction product was poured over ice cold water and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate. Recrystallisation was effected with appropriate solvent as shown in Table 3.

Preparation of bis oxazoles : The quantity of the 6-amino-7-hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin taken was (0.01 mole), twice the quantity of the dicarboxylic acid (0.005 mole). The reaction was maintained at 140° for 2 hr and then at 160° for 4 hr. The reaction product was worked out as above.

Preparation of 2-(3-heteraryl)-coumarino-(3',4', : 4,5)-oxazoles : Polyphosphoric acid was prepared as above and a mixture of 3-amino-4-hydroxy-coumarin⁹ (0.005 mole) and appropriate acid (0.005 mole) was dropped into it. The reaction mixture was heated first at $150-60^\circ$ for 2 hr and then at $200-205^\circ$ for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured over ice water and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bicarbonate. Recrystallisation details are included in Tables 3A, 3B and 3C.

TABLE 3A

Sl. No.	2-(Heteraryl)-4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5) oxazole	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of recrystallisation
1.	2-(3-Coumarinyl)-	225	60	Dioxane
2.	2-(6-Methyl-3-coumarinyl)-	275	60	Dioxane
3.	2-(8-Methyl-3-coumarinyl)-	356	60	Dioxane
4.	2-(6-Bromo-3-coumarinyl)-	330	60	Dioxane
5.	2-(5,6-Benzo-3-coumarinyl)-	315	40	Dioxane
6.	2-(2-Naphthyl)-	325	70	Benzene
7.	2-(1-Naphthyl)-	308	60	Benzene
8.	2-(p-Toluyyl)-	280	75	Benzene
9.	2-(Benzyl)-	288	50	Benzene
10.	1-(3-Pyridyl)-	325	60	Benzene
11.	2-(4-Pyridyl)-	320	60	Benzene
12.	2-(o-toluyyl)-	268	75	Benzene

TABLE 3B

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of recrystallisation
1.	Bis-[4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5)-oxazolo] methane	268	40	Dioxane
2.	Bis [4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5)-oxazolo] ethylene	325	40	Dioxane
3.	Bis-1,4-[4'-methyl-3'-phenylcoumarino-(6',7': 4,5)-oxazolo] benzene	272	60	Dioxane

TABLE 3C

Sl. No.	2-(8-Heteraryl)-coumarino-(3',4': 4,5) oxazole	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of recrystallisation
1.	2-(3-Coumarinyl)-	278	50	Dioxane
2.	2-(5,6-benzo-3-coumarinyl)-	290	40	Dioxane
3.	2-(8-Methyl-3-coumarinyl)-	295	50	Dioxane

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